

Kinetic studies of Ag^I-catalysed oxidation of maltose by vanadium(v) in perchloric acid medium : A mechanistic approach

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Abstract : The kinetics of Ag^I-catalysed oxidation of maltose by vanadium(v) in perchloric acid medium have been studied at 313 K. The reaction follows complex kinetics, being first order each in maltose and vanadium(v). The reaction rates increase with the increase in [H⁺]. Variation of ionic strength of the medium and addition of various amounts of salt had no effect on the rate indicating that the molecular species was involved in the rate determining step. Reactions were studied at different temperatures and activation parameters have been evaluated. The rate law in conformity with the observed kinetic data has been derived as

$$-d \ln [V^{5+}]/dt = k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 k_2 k_3 [\text{maltose}] [\text{Ag}^+] / \{k_{-1}(k_{-2} + k_3) + k_2 k_3 [\text{Ag}^+]\}$$

The high negative value of ΔS^\ddagger and positive ΔH^\ddagger show the formation of more ordered activated complex and highly solvated transition state.

Keywords : Kinetics, mechanism, maltose, vanadium(v), oxidation.

Introduction

Several workers¹ have studied the redox polymerization of vinyl monomers initiated by transition metal ions in their higher oxidation states and reported the mechanistic details¹. Kinetics of polymerization of acrylonitrile by vanadium(v)-potassium thiocyanate have been studied and reported that the reaction involving initiation by the free radicals produced by the interaction of vanadium(v) with thiocyanate and the termination by mutual interaction of the growing radicals. Vanadium(v) has been widely used as a powerful oxidant of different classes of organic and inorganic compounds². Littler and Waters^{2h} have shown that the kinetics of oxidation of cyclohexanone in aqueous sulphuric acid medium showing unit dependence in substrate as well as [H⁺] at constant ionic strength. Reported²ⁱ the first order kinetics each in vanadium(v) and substrate in oxidation of methyl ethyl ketone by vanadium(v) in dilute sulphuric acid and observed the formation of an intermediate complex between ketone and vanadium(v). The purpose of this study is to determine the kinetic parameters of the catalysed reaction using Ag^I with respect to each reactant of the reactions, as well as to present a suitable reaction mechanism and can be used

for the oxidation of many organic compounds and provide a condition for the estimation of these organic compounds.

Results and discussion

The reactions were carried out with varying concentrations of vanadium(v) in the range $(2.0-5.0) \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³ but at constant [H⁺], [maltose], [Ag⁺], ionic strength and temperature of 5.0×10^{-1} mol dm⁻³, 12.5×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, 0.51 mol dm⁻³ and 313 K respectively. The average pseudo-first order rate constant (k_{obs}) was found to be $(11.25 \pm 0.75) \times 10^{-5}$ s⁻¹ indicates that the reaction is first order with respect to vanadium(v).

$$-d[V^{5+}]/dt = k[V^{5+}]$$

$$-d \ln [V^{5+}]/dt = k_{\text{obs}} \quad (1)$$

The pseudo-first order rate constants were also determined at different concentrations of maltose in the range $(2.0-8.0) \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³ but at constant [H⁺], [V⁵⁺], [Ag⁺], ionic strength and temperature of 5.0×10^{-1} mol dm⁻³, 3.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, 5.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³, 0.508 mol dm⁻³ and 313 K respectively.

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_s[\text{maltose}] \quad (2)$$

Plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ against $\log [\text{maltose}]$ gives straight line with a slope of unity, showing first order in [maltose]. In $0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ HClO}_4$, the values of k_s are $(6.91 \pm 0.11) \times 10^{-2}$, $(9.21 \pm 0.23) \times 10^{-2}$, $(13.96 \pm 0.21) \times 10^{-2}$ and $(25.28 \pm 0.24) \times 10^{-2} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at the temperatures 308, 313, 318 and 323 K, respectively.

The rate of reaction increases with increase of $[\text{Ag}^+]$. The kinetics were studied at varying $[\text{Ag}^+]$ at 3.0×10^{-3} , 6.0×10^{-3} , 9.0×10^{-3} and $12.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ by keeping other parameters constant, the catalytic ratios (k_{cat}/k_0) are 1.949, 2.147, 2.273 and 2.352 respectively indicating the positive catalytic effect of $[\text{Ag}^+]$ on the rate of reaction. From experimental facts, the dependence of rate on $[\text{Ag}^+]$ and [maltose] can be expressed as

$$k_{\text{obs}} = m[\text{Ag}^+][\text{maltose}]/\{n + p[\text{Ag}^+]\} \quad (3)$$

$$1/k_{\text{obs}} = n/m[\text{maltose}][\text{Ag}^+] + p/m[\text{maltose}] \quad (4)$$

where m , n and p are expressed in terms of different rate constants. The effect of $[\text{H}^+]$ on the rate of reaction was investigated at different hydrogen ion concentration but at constant ionic strength. The ionic strength was maintained by the addition of sodium perchlorate. The rate of reaction increases with increase in hydrogen ion concentration (Table 1).

The plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $-\text{H}_0$ (Hammett acidity function)³ are linear with slope equal to 0.218 in the $[\text{H}^+]$ range $0.75\text{--}2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (Fig. 1). However, the plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $\log [\text{H}^+]$ are linear with slope equal to 0.333 (Fig. 2). The effect of $[\text{NaClO}_4]$ was studied to establish the nature of intermediate species in rate determining step. It was observed that the rate constant is independent of the ionic strength of the medium, indicates that at least one of the reacting species in rate determining step was molecular in nature⁴ (Table 1). It has been reported⁵ that when vanadium salts such as sodium metavanadate, ammonium metavanadate or V_2O_3 are dissolved in aqueous acidic medium, they exist as protonated species such as $\text{V}(\text{OH})_3^{2+}$. The temperature effect was studied in the range 308–323 K and the enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) was calculated from the slope of the plot of $\log (k_{\text{obs}}/T)$ vs $1/T$ (Fig. 3). The values of activation parameters, ΔH^\ddagger , E_a , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger are calculated (Table 1). The very high values of negative ΔS^\ddagger and of positive ΔH^\ddagger suggests the

formation of more ordered activated complex and the transition state is highly solvated⁶.

Mechanism :

The above kinetic evidences can be explained by considering the following reaction mechanism :

where $\text{R} = \text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_{10}$

Maltose has been oxidised by vanadium(V) via unstable intermediate complex followed by the fission of C-C bond to form reaction product. The OH group of maltose combines with $\text{V}(\text{OH})_3^{2+}$, the most reactive species⁵ of

Table 1. Effect of [H⁺], ionic strength on the rate of reaction and values of thermodynamic parameters

[Maltose] = 2.5 × 10 ⁻³ mol dm ⁻³ , [V ⁵⁺] = 3.0 × 10 ⁻³ mol dm ⁻³ , [Ag ⁺] = 5.0 × 10 ⁻³ mol dm ⁻³ , Temp. = 40°					
[NaClO ₄] (mol dm ⁻³)	0	0.50	1.0	1.25	1.50
[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	2.0	1.50	1.0	0.75	0.50
k _{obs} × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)	30.55 ± 0.52	28.75 ± 0.66	22.65 ± 0.71	21.61 ± 0.75	17.12 ± 0.72
[NaClO ₄] × 10 ² (mol dm ⁻³)		1.50	3.0	4.50	6.0
I (mol dm ⁻³)		0.525	0.54	0.555	0.57
k _{obs} × 10 ⁵ (s ⁻¹)		8.63 ± 0.35	9.01 ± 0.13	8.75 ± 0.59	8.26 ± 0.74
Thermodynamic parameters		ΔH [#] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	E _a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS [#] (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG [#] (kJ mol ⁻¹)
		91.81 ± 0.26	97.01 ± 0.11	-23.36 ± 0.43	84.49 ± 0.21

Fig. 1. Plot of log k_{obs} vs -H₀ at 40°. [Maltose] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [V⁵⁺] = 3.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Ag⁺] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, ionic strength = 2.008 mol dm⁻³.

Fig. 2. Plot of log k_{obs} vs log [H⁺] at 40°. [Maltose] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [V⁵⁺] = 3.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Ag⁺] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, ionic strength = 2.008 mol dm⁻³.

vanadium(V) to form complex₁. Complex₁, subsequently combines with Ag⁺ to form complex₂. Complex₂ forms complex₃ by the liberation of H₃O⁺, which leads to the formation of aldehyde (RCHO), V³⁺ and regeneration of Ag⁺. The hydrated form of aldehyde ultimately combines with V(OH)₃²⁺ to form reaction product. Reported earlier⁷ that maltose has been oxidised by cerium(IV) via

Fig. 3. Plot of log (k_{obs}/T) vs 1/T. [Maltose] = 2.5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [V⁵⁺] = 3.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Ag⁺] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [H⁺] = 5.0 × 10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³, ionic strength = 0.508 mol dm⁻³.

complex formation. The rate law from the above mechanism could be written as

$$\frac{-d[V^{5+}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3 [S][V^{5+}][Ag^+]}{k_{-1} k_{-2} + k_{-1} k_3 + k_2 k_3 [Ag^+]} \quad (14)$$

where S stands for maltose

The above rate law explains the first order dependence of rate on each in [maltose] and [V⁵⁺] and fractional order dependence on [Ag⁺]. The eq. (14) could be written as

$$k_{obs} = \frac{-d \ln [V^{5+}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3 [S][Ag^+]}{k_{-1} k_{-2} + k_{-1} k_3 + k_2 k_3 [Ag^+]} \quad (15)$$

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3 [S][Ag^+]}{k_{-1}(k_{-2} + k_3) + k_2 k_3 [Ag^+]} \quad (16)$$

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_1 k_2 k_3 [S][Ag^+]}{k_{-1} k' + k_2 k_3 [Ag^+]} \quad (17)$$

where $k' = k_{-2} + k_3$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{m[\text{S}][\text{Ag}^+]}{n + p[\text{Ag}^+]} \quad (18)$$

where $m = k_1 k_2 k_3$, $n = k_{-1} k'$ and $p = k_2 k_3$

By taking reciprocals of eq. (18)

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{n + p[\text{Ag}^+]}{m[\text{S}][\text{Ag}^+]}$$

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{n}{m[\text{S}][\text{Ag}^+]} + \frac{p}{m[\text{S}]} \quad (19)$$

where m , n and p are rate constants and expressed in terms of different rate constants.

From the slope, intercept on the $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ axis and extrapolated intercept on $1/[\text{Ag}^+]$ axis, the values of $n/m[\text{S}]$, $p/m[\text{S}]$ and $-1/n$ were calculated. A plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{S}]$, at constant $[\text{V}^{5+}]$ was linear with a small intercepts on y-axis, offering kinetic support for complex formation. The absence of polymerization when acrylonitrile was added to the reaction mixture under nitrogen atmosphere indicated the absence of free radical intermediates.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. Stoke solution of vanadium(v) was prepared in double-distilled water by dissolving appropriate amount of ammonium metavanadate and perchloric acid. The stock solutions of sodium perchlorate, maltose and silver nitrate were prepared in double distilled water. Vanadium(v) solution was standardized by redox titration⁸. Kinetic experiments were carried out in a thermostate at 40° in aqueous perchloric acid medium. An aliquot (5 ml) of the reaction mixture was withdrawn at different intervals of time and the reaction was quenched by pouring it into a known excess of standard Fe^{2+} solution. The unused Fe^{2+} was titrated against standard vanadium(v) solution using barium diphenylamine sulphonate as an indicator.

Stoichiometry :

The reaction mixture containing maltose, acid, V^{5+} and Ag^+ were kept until the completion of the reaction. The unconsumed V^{5+} was determined by titrimetry. For-

mic acid was identified⁹ the main product of oxidation of maltose. The stoichiometry thus determined was found to be 24 moles of V^{5+} to 1 mole of maltose. Thus, the overall stoichiometric equation could be written as

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